

BIOTRAILS

Project acronym: BIOTRAILS
Title: Nexus Framework for biodiversity-relevant transformative change
Grant Agreement number: 101082008

Leverage point identification and implementation in biodiversity relevant value chains

Description: Technical publication
Lead beneficiary: adelphi
Document type: R – Document, report
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Contributions from: CIAT, HAPO, KNUST
Project URL: www.biotrailsproject.eu

Funded by
the European Union

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AFI	Attitudes-Facilitators-Infrastructure
ASM	Artisanal and small-scale Mining
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
LP	Leverage Point

ABSTRACT

Global biodiversity decline is significantly driven by unsustainable value chains across multiple economic sectors. The EU Horizon project BIOTRAILS developed and tested a framework for the identification of pathways towards transformative change in biodiversity-relevant value chains. This report focuses on describing the methodologies applied and summarises the findings from the project. The framework combines the Leverage Points Framework with the Attitudes-Facilitators-Infrastructure (AFI) Framework through a three-stage participatory methodology, integrating systematic literature reviews with stakeholder engagement. Applied to four diverse value chains – cocoa production in Peru, forest-based cultural products in Brazil, fisheries and aquaculture in Greece, and artisanal small-scale gold mining in Ghana – the methodology demonstrates that strategic intervention points can be systematically identified and contextualised when the framework is adapted to local environmental, social, economic, and institutional conditions. Despite differences in sectors, geographies, and sustainability challenges, the consistent methodological approach enabled the identification of both common patterns and context-specific leverage points across all case studies.

This report provides practical guidance, tools, and lessons learned for practitioners, policymakers, and researchers seeking to apply the framework to other value chains, demonstrating that the methodology is effective when tailored to the specific contexts.

1. INTRODUCTION

Global biodiversity is experiencing unprecedented decline, driven by unsustainable production and consumption patterns across numerous economic sectors. Value chains – from agricultural commodities to extractive industries – play a central role in this crisis, contributing to habitat destruction, pollution, species loss, and ecosystem degradation [1].

At the same time, these value chains support the livelihoods of millions of people worldwide, particularly smallholder farmers, artisanal producers, and local communities who depend on natural resources for their economic survival. Addressing this dual challenge requires transformative change: systemic shifts that reconcile environmental sustainability with economic equity and social inclusion.

Transformative change seeks to fundamentally reshape the structures, values, and behaviours that govern value chains by identifying and activating leverage points that can trigger cascading effects and produce disproportionately large outcomes. Recent frameworks, including the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework adopted under the Convention on Biological Diversity, emphasise the need for such systemic approaches to halt and reverse biodiversity decline by 2030 [2].

This report emerges from research conducted under the European Union Horizon project BIOTRAILS that focuses on biodiversity-relevant transformative change. The project examined four globally significant value chains across diverse geographies and sectors: cocoa production in Peru, forest-based cultural products in Brazil, fisheries and aquaculture in Greece, and artisanal small-scale gold mining in Ghana. Each value chain faces distinct environmental, social, and economic challenges, yet they share common patterns of unsustainable resource use, marginalisation of smallholder producers, and insufficient integration of biodiversity considerations into decision-making processes. Through rigorous analysis combining theoretical frameworks with participatory stakeholder engagement, the project identified leverage points for transformative change and designed transitional pathways tailored to each context. The results are publicly available on the

projects' website¹

This technical report synthesises the methodologies, tools, and findings from Deliverable D2.3² and Deliverable 2.4³ to provide accessible guidance for practitioners, policymakers, researchers, and value chain stakeholders seeking to apply similar approaches in their own contexts. It will furthermore present the key results from each case study, focusing on the environmental, economic, and social changes and conclude by presenting recommendations for readers considering applying the same frameworks and tools to comparable value chains, sectors and/or geographic contexts.

Key Principles and Limitations

This report is grounded in evidence drawn directly from the original project deliverable and associated research. The four case studies represent specific geographic and sectoral contexts, and whilst they offer valuable insights, findings cannot be uncritically generalised to all value chains or regions. The leverage points identified and interventions proposed reflect the particular environmental, social, economic, and institutional conditions of Peru, Brazil, Greece, and Ghana. Readers seeking to apply these approaches elsewhere must carefully consider local contexts, stakeholder dynamics, and enabling conditions.

Furthermore, the participatory stakeholder engagement activities conducted as part of the project engaged diverse stakeholders but may not have captured the perspectives of all affected groups. The leverage points identified through these workshops represent collective priorities at a specific moment in time and should be understood as provisional rather than definitive. Transformative change is inherently dynamic and contested; pathways must be continuously refined through ongoing dialogue and adaptive management.

Despite these limitations, the frameworks, methods, and insights presented in this report offer robust and transferable tools for advancing biodiversity-relevant transformative change across diverse value chains and contexts.

2. Methodology and Tools

This chapter outlines the analytical frameworks and methodological approaches used to identify leverage points for transformative change across the four value chains. By integrating insights from academic literature with stakeholder knowledge through stakeholder engagement, analytical depth and practical relevance are ensured in the projects' work.

2.1 CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATION: TWO COMPLEMENTARY FRAMEWORKS

The analysis draws upon two theoretical frameworks that together provide a comprehensive lens for examining systemic change in value chains. These frameworks, the Leverage Points Framework and the Attitudes-Facilitators-Infrastructure (AFI) Framework, complement one another by addressing change at multiple scales and through multiple pathways. The Leverage Points Framework operates primarily at the macro-systemic level, identifying strategic intervention points within complex systems, whilst the AFI Framework focuses on the micro-level mechanisms

¹ <https://biotrailsproject.eu/resources/>

² https://biotrailsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/BIOTRAILS_D2.3_Framework-of-transitional-pathways-and-leverage-points-A.pdf

³ https://biotrailsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/BIOTRAILS_D2.4_Framework-of-transitional-pathways-and-leverage-points-B_final.pdf

that shape individual and collective behaviours. Together, they enable a holistic approach to designing transitional pathways towards sustainability.

2.1.1 The Leverage Points Framework

The Leverage Points Framework provides a systems-thinking approach to understanding where strategic interventions can generate disproportionately large effects within complex systems. Originally conceptualised by systems theorist Donella Meadows in 1999, the framework posits that not all intervention points within a system are equally powerful. Some changes, such as adjusting parameters or constants, produce relatively modest, linear effects. Others, such as altering the goals, paradigms, or underlying values that govern system behaviour, can trigger cascading transformations that fundamentally reshape system outcomes [3, 4].

The framework organises potential intervention points into a hierarchy ranging from shallow (less transformative) to deep (more transformative: targeting e.g. fundamental rules or values) leverage points. This hierarchical structure does not imply that shallow leverage points are unimportant; rather, it recognises that deeper interventions are more likely to produce systemic and enduring change [5].

For the purposes of biodiversity conservation and sustainable value chain development, the framework was expanded by Chan et al. [6] in the context of the Intergovernmental Science–Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) Global Assessment. They identified eight specific leverage points particularly relevant for creating pathways to sustainability at multiple scales. These eight categories (see Figure 1) provide a structured typology for analysing where strategic interventions might be most effective and are complemented by five cross-cutting levers that can be applied across multiple leverage points to enhance their effectiveness and amplify the impact of the interventions by enabling supporting conditions and governance mechanisms.

Figure 1: Levers and leverage points for pathways to sustainability. Source: Chan et al. (2020) [6].

2.1.2 The Attitudes–Facilitators–Infrastructure (AFI) Framework

Whilst the Leverage Points Framework provides a macro-systemic perspective, the AFI Framework focuses specifically on the determinants of sustainable lifestyles and consumption behaviours. Developed by Akenji [7] and refined by Akenji et al. [8], the framework recognises that individual

behaviours are not simply the result of personal preferences or rational choices, but are profoundly shaped by the socio–environmental context in which people live.

The AFI Framework identifies three interdependent categories of determinants that influence behaviour: **Attitudes** represent the values, beliefs, and preferences that individuals and groups hold regarding sustainability. **Facilitators** are the mechanisms, resources, and enabling conditions that translate intentions into actions. And **Infrastructure** refers to the physical systems, provisioning arrangements, and default options that structure everyday life.

Eleven driving factors are identified that shape the three determinants (see Figure 2). By mapping how those interact with attitudes, facilitators, and infrastructure, the AFI Framework provides a structured approach to identify barriers to sustainable behaviour and potential intervention opportunities.

Figure 2: Motivations, drivers and determinants influencing lifestyles and consumption. Source: Vilchis Tella and Trimmer (2018) [9].

2.1.3 Synergies between the Frameworks

The LP Framework and the AFI Framework are complementary in several important ways. The Leverage Points Framework offers a broad taxonomy of intervention domains across entire systems, from global trade relationships to cultural paradigms. The AFI Framework, conversely, provides granular analysis of the specific mechanisms through which individuals and communities adopt (or fail to adopt) sustainable practices. Together, they enable analysis at multiple scales: from macro-level structural changes to micro-level behavioural shifts and allow the design of interventions with both systemic impact and behavioural feasibility in mind.

2.2 OPERATIONALISING THE FRAMEWORKS: A THREE-STAGE METHODOLOGY

To translate these conceptual frameworks into actionable insights for the four case study value chains, a three-stage methodology was employed. The first stage involved systematic literature reviews to identify potential leverage points based on existing research and documented experiences from similar contexts. The second stage employed participatory stakeholder workshops to validate, refine, and expand these leverage points through direct engagement with value chain stakeholders. The third stage contains of a comparative analysis for each case study individually as well as across the different value chains. This combined approach ensured that the analysis was both theoretically informed and empirically grounded.

2.2.1 Stage One: Literature-Based Identification of Leverage Points

For each of the four value chains, cocoa production in Peru, forest-based cultural products in Brazil, fisheries and aquaculture in Greece, and artisanal gold mining in Ghana, comprehensive literature reviews were conducted to identify potential leverage points for transformative change. These reviews synthesised academic research, policy documents, technical reports, and case studies from similar value chains and geographic contexts.

They were structured according to the eight categories of leverage points identified by Chan et al. [6], systematically examining evidence related to each category within the specific value chain context.

This systematic approach ensured comprehensive coverage of potential intervention domains whilst maintaining analytical consistency across the four case studies. The literature reviews produced initial catalogues of leverage points for each value chain, documented in structured tables that specified the leverage point category, the specific intervention proposed, and the evidence base supporting its relevance.⁴

2.2.2 Stage Two: Participatory Validation through Policy Workshops

The leverage points identified through literature were then subsequently validated and refined through participatory stakeholder workshops conducted in each of the four case study regions: Ucayali, Peru (cocoa); Rondônia, Brazil (forest-based cultural products); the Mediterranean region (fisheries and aquaculture); and Kumasi, Ghana (artisanal gold mining). These workshops brought together diverse stakeholders directly involved in or affected by the respective value chains.

Participants in the participatory stakeholder workshops represented multiple stakeholder groups, including:

- Smallholder producers (farmers, fishers, artisanal miners, artisans)
- Producer cooperatives and associations
- Private sector actors (traders, processors, exporters)
- Government officials (from relevant ministries and regulatory agencies)
- Civil society organisations and non-governmental organisations
- Research institutions and universities
- Local community representatives, including Indigenous Peoples where relevant

Gender balance and representation of marginalised groups were explicitly sought to ensure inclusive participation.

⁴ For the full results, see Deliverable 2.3 of the project: https://biotrailproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/BIOTRAILS_D2.3_Framework-of-transitional-pathways-and-leverage-points-A.pdf

A structured three-step process designed to elicit stakeholder knowledge whilst maintaining analytical coherence was employed in the workshops:

Step 1: Identifying and Ranking Critical Challenges

Participants engaged in collaborative exercises to identify the most pressing social, economic, and environmental challenges facing their value chain. Through facilitated discussions and participatory ranking methods (such as voting and prioritisation matrices), stakeholders collectively determined which problems were most urgent, most widespread, or most detrimental to sustainability. This step ensured that subsequent leverage point identification was grounded in stakeholders' lived experiences and priorities.

Step 2: Developing Actionable Leverage Points

Building on the challenges identified in Step 1, participants brainstormed specific, actionable ideas for addressing these challenges. Facilitators introduced the concept of leverage points and the eight-category framework, but stakeholders were encouraged to propose solutions in their own terms based on their practical knowledge and contextual understanding. This step generated concrete intervention ideas that reflected local capacities, institutional contexts, and cultural appropriateness.

Step 3: Prioritising Leverage Points by Feasibility and Impact

The proposed leverage points were then evaluated according to two criteria: their potential impact on sustainability outcomes (environmental, social, and economic) and their feasibility given existing resources, institutional arrangements, and political contexts. Through structured scoring or deliberative discussion, participants prioritised which leverage points offered the most promising pathways for transformative change. This prioritisation ensured that the final recommendations balanced ambition with practicality.

The outputs of the policy workshops were documented in structured tables analogous to those produced through literature reviews, enabling systematic comparison.⁵

2.2.3 Stage Three: Identifying Commonalities and Contrasts

Following completion of both the literature reviews and stakeholder workshops, a comparative analysis was conducted for each value chain to identify commonalities and contrasts between the two sets of leverage points. This analysis served multiple purposes:

- **Validation:** When leverage points identified through literature were also independently proposed by stakeholders, this convergence provided strong validation of their relevance and importance. Commonalities indicated robust, widely recognised opportunities for intervention.
- **Contextualisation:** Differences between literature-based and stakeholder-identified leverage points often revealed important contextual specificities. Such contrasts highlighted the need to adapt generic recommendations to local conditions.
- **Identifying Gaps:** Contrasts could also reveal blind spots in existing research or limitations in stakeholder awareness. For example, if literature emphasised technological solutions not mentioned by stakeholders, this might indicate barriers to knowledge transfer or technology access. Conversely, if stakeholders proposed interventions not documented in literature, this might point to underexplored pathways deserving further research.
- **Comprehensiveness:** The combination of literature-based and participatory approaches ensured a more comprehensive identification of leverage points than either method alone could achieve.

For each value chain, the commonalities and contrasts were analysed thematically and documented narratively, providing nuanced understanding of where consensus existed and where different

⁵ The final tables can be found in [Deliverable 2.4](#).

perspectives offered complementary insights.

3. Case Study Application

The emphasis of this chapter is placed on demonstrating the practical application of the analytical frameworks and validation processes, followed by brief summaries of the key results. This summary illustrates how targeted interventions at strategic leverage points can trigger transformative change across environmental, economic, and social dimensions.

The methodology described above was applied systematically across all four value chains representing diverse sectors, geographies, and sustainability challenges. Whilst the conceptual frameworks and procedural steps remained consistent, their application was adapted to the specific characteristics of each case:

Peru (Cocoa): The methodology examined leverage points for transforming cocoa production from a driver of deforestation and social inequality into a model of agroforestry, biodiversity conservation, and farmer empowerment. The policy laboratory in Ucayali engaged over thirty stakeholders from across the value chain.

Brazil (Forest-Based Cultural Products): The analysis focused on Indigenous communities producing cultural products (crafts, textiles, natural cosmetics) from forest resources in the Amazon region. The methodology addressed how to strengthen Indigenous autonomy, cultural preservation, and sustainable forest management whilst expanding market access.

Greece (Fisheries and Aquaculture): The Mediterranean context presented challenges related to overfishing, habitat degradation, and the environmental impacts of aquaculture. The methodology explored pathways towards sustainable fishing practices, ecosystem-based management, and responsible aquaculture expansion.

Ghana (Artisanal Gold Mining): The case of small-scale gold mining presented particularly pressing environmental challenges, including mercury contamination, deforestation, and land degradation, alongside social issues such as informal labour and conflicts over land use. The workshop in Kumasi engaged, amongst others, artisanal miners and local community representatives.

Despite their diversity, these case studies shared a common methodological foundation, enabling cross-case synthesis whilst respecting context-specific differences. The emphasis of this chapter is placed on demonstrating the practical application of the analytical framework and validation processes, followed by a brief introduction and some results of the case studies.

3.1 APPLICATION OF METHODOLOGY

As described previously, the methodology was applied in three stages. First, a comprehensive literature review identified potential leverage points across the eight categories of the Leverage Points Framework, drawing on academic research, policy analyses, and documented experiences from other regions engaging in the same value chains worldwide. This review produced an initial catalogue of intervention opportunities tailored to the context of each case study specifically.⁶

Second, these literature-based leverage points were validated in a first round of participatory stakeholder workshops (see Table 2). Through structured, guided focus group discussions, participants identified in a first step the most critical challenges facing their specific sector, discussed and proposed actionable leverage points to address these challenges afterwards, and eventually prioritised the proposed interventions based on their feasibility and potential impact.

⁶ A detailed description of the leverage points identified in this initial step can be found in Deliverable D2.3 of the project. Available under: https://biotrailsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/BIOTRAILS_D2.3_Framework-of-transitional-pathways-and-leverage-points-A.pdf

Table 1: Initial participatory stakeholder workshops.

	Peru	Brazil	Greece	Ghana
Date	October 2024	October 2023	January 2024	November 2023
Location	Ucayali, Peru	Brasília & Rondônia, Brazil	Athens, Greece	Kumasi, Ghana
No. of Participants	28	25	10	50

Third, a qualitative thematic analysis was used to identify commonalities and contrasts, identify actionable LPs, create a positive scenario and develop targeted interventions for each case. The thematic analysis was refined through continuous feedback loops with the stakeholders through in-project communication platforms and a second round of in-person workshops (see Table 2).

Table 2: Second round of participatory stakeholder workshops.

	Peru	Brazil	Greece	Ghana
Date	May 2025	October 2024	May 2025	March 2025
Location	Pucallpa, Peru	Brasília, Brazil	Athens, Greece	Kumasi, Ghana
No. of Participants	6	32	10	39

Each workshop was accompanied by detailed documentation of the data collected by using recordings, discussion notes, stakeholders' feedback, and pictures of whiteboard activities, such as prioritization matrices. To perform the qualitative thematic analysis the data was subject to close review to identify key points and discernible patterns which in a second step were organized into broader themes. Following a subsequent refinement through discussions with the stakeholders in the second workshops series – to ensure consistency and accuracy of the results – a comparison was made of the key themes, recurring challenges and proposed solutions, both within and across country contexts. The thematic synthesis allowed the determination of shared LPs as well as context- and country-specific priorities and obstacles.

By the end of the project, a final series of workshops was conducted in each case country (see Table 3) to introduce and train stakeholders on the tools developed by the project, and to discuss and reflect, once again, the final results – to foster implementation of the interventions developed.

Table 3: Final participatory stakeholder workshops.

	Peru	Brazil	Greece	Ghana
Date	October 2025	September 2025	September 2025	October 2025
Location	Ucayali, Peru	Brasília, Brazil	Athens, Greece	Kumasi, Ghana
No. of Participants	16	14	7	27

3.2 CASE COUNTRY CONTEXT AND RESULTS

The analysis revealed both convergence and divergence between literature-based and stakeholder-identified leverage points. The following sub-chapter highlights the value chain and country-specific challenges and gives a short summary of some results drawn from the participatory stakeholder workshops⁷.

⁷ To review the results in detail, see [Deliverable 2.4](#).

3.2.1 Cocoa in Peru

Peru ranks as the second-largest producer of organic cocoa globally and is home to 60 per cent of the world's cocoa genetic diversity. Over 120,000 smallholder farmers cultivate cocoa on plots averaging two to five hectares, making cocoa farming an essential, though often supplementary, source of income for many rural households [10]. A historic milestone was achieved in 2024, when cocoa exports surpassed USD 1.3 billion, primarily to markets in the United States, the Netherlands, and Belgium [11].

Despite these economic achievements, the cocoa value chain faces significant sustainability challenges. Environmental pressures include deforestation driven by agricultural expansion, biodiversity loss due to monoculture practices, and soil degradation from intensive agrochemical use. Social challenges encompass widespread informality, poor working conditions, inequitable value distribution along the supply chain, and limited transparency regarding production practices [12]. Climate change further exacerbates these difficulties through prolonged droughts, torrential rainfall, and wildfires that threaten livelihoods.⁸ Whilst rising global cocoa prices have offered short-term economic relief, they risk incentivising further deforestation and undermining long-term sustainability efforts.

Key Results: Interventions and Transformative Change

Based on the validated leverage points, a set of targeted interventions was designed in the workshop. These included:

- Providing financial incentives and technical support for farmers to integrate cocoa cultivation with diverse tree species, restoring degraded lands whilst enhancing biodiversity and carbon sequestration;
- Implementing geolocation-based traceability systems and blockchain technologies to monitor cocoa from farm to market, ensuring alignment with international standards such as the EU Deforestation Regulation;
- Supporting cooperatives to enable collective bargaining, resource sharing, and diversification into value-added products (such as processed cocoa or artisanal chocolate);
- Developing community-based programmes to promote sustainable practices and consumer awareness campaigns to encourage ethical cocoa consumption;
- Investing in research on sustainable agricultural technologies, including wastewater treatment systems and certification schemes to validate sustainable practices.

These interventions are anticipated to trigger interconnected environmental, economic, and social changes. Environmentally, agroforestry adoption would restore degraded ecosystems, enhance soil health, sequester carbon, and create habitats for diverse species, whilst reduced agrochemical use would lower pollution levels. Economically, income diversification and transparent traceability systems would increase farmer resilience to market volatility and ensure fair compensation for sustainable practices. Socially, community-driven education would instil environmental stewardship values, whilst recognising local producers as custodians of sustainable cocoa would revitalise cultural pride and strengthen community bonds.

Positive feedback loops include the self-reinforcing economic and environmental benefits of agroforestry and growing consumer demand for sustainably sourced cocoa strengthening producer commitment to certification. Potential negative feedback loops that require mitigation include the high upfront costs of traceability systems and certification potentially discouraging smallholder participation, weak enforcement of anti-deforestation regulations undermining intervention effectiveness, and short-term economic pressures pushing farmers towards

⁸ Please see [Deliverable 3.7](#) and [Deliverable 3.8](#) of the project for further analysis.

immediate gains over long-term sustainability.

A positive scenario was articulated to serve as an aspirational vision for stakeholders. In this envisioned future, cocoa production operates in harmony with the environment through widespread agroforestry; farmers thrive economically through diversified income streams and cooperative support; local producers are celebrated for their contributions to sustainability; and the value chain aligns seamlessly with international ethical trade standards, becoming a global model for demonstrating that sustainability and profitability can coexist.

3.2.2 Handicrafts in Brazil

The Brazilian case study focuses on Indigenous communities in the Amazon region of Rondônia who produce forest-based cultural products, including handicrafts, textiles, natural cosmetics, and traditional artefacts. These communities depend on sustainably harvested forest resources for both cultural expression and economic livelihoods [13]. However, the value chain faces challenges including external pressures from deforestation and land-use change, limited market access and low bargaining power for Indigenous producers, inadequate recognition of Indigenous intellectual property and traditional knowledge, and insufficient infrastructure for processing and distribution.

Key results: Leverage Points, Interventions and transformative changes

The comparative analysis of LPs revealed important commonalities. Both literature and stakeholders emphasised the importance of sustainability in forest resource management, reducing extraction pressures whilst maintaining cultural practices; addressing social and economic inequalities by empowering Indigenous producers through fair trade mechanisms, capacity building, and collective action; and ensuring justice and inclusion by recognising Indigenous rights, engaging local communities in conservation decision-making, and protecting traditional knowledge.

Contrasts also emerged. The literature emphasised broader systemic interventions such as developing consumer markets for ethically sourced cultural products and establishing international certification schemes, whilst stakeholders prioritised community-driven, locally appropriate solutions such as providing technical training in product development, strengthening local governance structures, and improving access to local and regional markets. The literature focused on technological innovations for product quality and traceability, whereas the policy laboratory emphasised grassroots innovations rooted in traditional knowledge and community-controlled resource management.

Interventions were designed across multiple leverage points, including:

- promoting awareness campaigns highlighting the cultural and environmental value of Indigenous products;
- supporting sustainable harvesting practices and reforestation to maintain forest ecosystems;
- launching community education programmes fostering environmental stewardship;
- providing appropriate financing mechanisms and capacity building for producer cooperatives;
- ensuring Indigenous participation in conservation governance; implementing traceability systems for responsible sourcing;
- investing in appropriate technologies that respect traditional knowledge;
- and fostering knowledge exchange between communities, researchers, and markets.

These interventions are expected to trigger transformative changes whereby Indigenous communities gain greater economic autonomy and market access whilst maintaining cultural

integrity. Forest ecosystems are conserved through sustainable harvesting regimes in alignment with traditional management practices and global consumers gain access to ethically sourced cultural products, creating market incentives for conservation.

The envisioned positive scenario involves thriving Indigenous economies based on valorised cultural production, intact forest ecosystems maintained through community stewardship, and robust traceability ensuring fair compensation and recognition.

3.2.3 Fish and Aquaculture Products in Greece

Greece is the third-largest aquaculture producer in the Mediterranean and the second-largest among European Union member states, with approximately 80 per cent of farmed fish exported internationally [14]. The Greek fishing fleet represents 19 per cent of the EU's total fleet and is dominated by small-scale coastal fishing, which accounts for 90 per cent of sector employment [15, 16, 17], Fisheries and aquaculture are deeply intertwined with Greece's maritime heritage and economic identity [18].

However, the value chain faces substantial environmental challenges. Overfishing has depleted fish stocks and disrupted marine ecosystems. Habitat degradation results from destructive fishing practices and poorly sited aquaculture operations that damage sensitive coastal and seabed habitats. Nutrient pollution from aquaculture effluents contributes to eutrophication, harming water quality and biodiversity. These environmental pressures threaten the sector's long-term viability, necessitating integrated policies balancing economic growth with environmental stewardship.

Key results: Leverage Points, Interventions and transformative challenges

The LPs comparative analysis revealed commonalities around prioritising ecosystem-based management approaches, addressing economic inequalities among small-scale producers, promoting education and awareness regarding sustainable seafood, and fostering innovation in eco-friendly aquaculture technologies. Contrasts centred on the literature's emphasis on international market differentiation and certification versus stakeholders' focus on strengthening local governance and enforcement mechanisms.

Interventions were designed to address multiple leverage points. These included:

- implementing science-based fishing quotas and marine protected areas to allow stock recovery;
- promoting offshore aquaculture to reduce coastal habitat impacts;
- adopting circular economy practices such as repurposing fish waste into fertilisers and fishmeal;
- transitioning to renewable energy in aquaculture operations;
- developing alternative, sustainable fish feed sources to reduce pressure on wild fish stocks;
- establishing traceability systems and certification schemes to ensure transparency and reward sustainable practices;
- launching public education campaigns on sustainable seafood consumption;
- and fostering knowledge exchange among producers, researchers, and policymakers.

Environmental changes anticipated include marine ecosystem recovery through reduced overfishing and habitat protection, lower pollution from circular economy practices and reduced agrochemical use, and enhanced biodiversity through effective marine protected areas. Economic changes include improved market access and premium prices for certified sustainable seafood, cost savings from renewable energy adoption, and strengthened competitiveness in international markets. Social changes encompass enhanced capacity and empowerment of small-scale

producers, particularly women and youth, and a culture of environmental stewardship fostered through education.

Positive feedback loops identified include economic and environmental synergies from circular economy practices incentivising further adoption, and growing consumer demand for sustainable seafood reinforcing producer commitment. Potential negative feedback loops requiring mitigation include high upfront costs of renewable energy and traceability systems potentially excluding small-scale producers, and weak enforcement of fishing regulations undermining intervention effectiveness.

3.2.4 Gold in Ghana

Gold production is central to Ghana's economy, with the country leading Africa in gold output [19]. The sector contributes 7.2 per cent to national GDP and approximately 56 per cent of mining industry output. Whilst large-scale commercial mines produce the majority of gold, artisanal and small-scale mining (ASM) – locally known as Galamsey (meaning "gather and sell") – accounts for 30 to 35 per cent of production [20]. An estimated 500,000 to one million Ghanaians work directly in ASM, with an additional 4.5 million indirectly dependent on the sector [21].

Despite its economic importance, ASM faces severe challenges. Socially, the sector is characterised by poor regulation, unsafe working conditions, and social conflicts, as much of the activity operates informally without oversight. Environmentally, ASM causes significant deforestation, land degradation, and biodiversity loss in Ghana's High Forest Zone, a globally recognised biodiversity hotspot. Mercury contamination from gold amalgamation threatens water bodies, soil, ecosystems, and human health. Competition with agriculture for land and labour results in farmland loss and further deforestation as displaced farmers expand into forested areas.

Key results: Leverage Points, Interventions and transformative changes

Leverage Points comparison revealed commonalities between literature-based and stakeholder-identified leverage points, including shared emphasis on environmental sustainability through mercury-free extraction technologies and land reclamation; addressing social and economic inequalities by formalising ASM operations and providing fair trade access; ensuring justice and inclusion through community participation in decision-making and resource management; and prioritising education and knowledge sharing through training programmes and awareness campaigns.

Contrasts reflected differences between systemic, technology-focused approaches in the literature versus practical, community-driven solutions emphasised by stakeholders. The literature highlighted international certification and traceability systems, whilst stakeholders prioritised localised governance structures and enforcement mechanisms rooted in community traditions.

Interventions were designed across the leverage point spectrum. These included:

raising awareness through local and international campaigns about ASM's environmental and social impacts;

- introducing mercury-free gold extraction technologies to reduce environmental and health risks;
- promoting circular economy practices such as recycling gold from electronic waste;
- launching community education programmes fostering environmental stewardship;
- providing financing mechanisms and capacity building to support ASM formalisation;
- ensuring marginalised groups (including women and youth) participate in decision-making;
- implementing traceability systems for responsible gold sourcing aligned with international ethical standards;
- promoting research on low-impact mining technologies;

- and developing training programmes on mercury-free technologies and environmental conservation.

Environmental changes anticipated include elimination of mercury contamination through adoption of safer extraction methods, ecosystem restoration through community-led land reclamation projects transforming degraded sites into productive landscapes supporting biodiversity conservation and agriculture, and reduced pressure on natural reserves through circular economy practices. Economic changes include improved livelihoods through ASM formalisation enabling access to ethical markets and fair trade certification, and enhanced transparency through traceability systems rewarding sustainable practices. Social changes encompass active community involvement in decision-making ensuring mining practices align with local needs and priorities, equitable access to resources and training for marginalised groups, and a culture of environmental stewardship fostered through education.

The positive scenario envisions Ghana's gold value chain as a benchmark for environmental sustainability, social equity, and economic resilience, where ASM drives community empowerment and sustainable development rather than degradation. Positive feedback loops include economic and environmental synergies from mercury-free technologies and land reclamation incentivising broader adoption, whilst potential negative feedback loops requiring mitigation include high initial costs deterring small-scale miners and weak regulatory enforcement allowing unsustainable practices to persist.

4. Recommendations

Whereas Chapter 3 focuses on the individual results of each case study, this chapter synthesises insights from all four case studies to identify cross-cutting lessons and scalable strategies for advancing transformative change in biodiversity-relevant value chains. As this technical report focuses on the methodological aspects, this chapter will continue with practical guidance for applying the methodology, and available tools and resources. Common themes emerging across all case studies, specific interventions identified for value chain transformation in general as well as broader systemic LPs can be retrieved from Deliverable 2.4.⁹

4.1 PRACTICAL GUIDANCE FOR APPLYING THE METHODOLOGY

Readers seeking to apply the Leverage Points Framework and participatory validation methodology to their own contexts should consider the following practical steps and considerations, that were derived from practical experiences and lessons learned from the BIOTRAILS project.

1. **Conducting Literature Reviews:** Begin by systematically reviewing existing research, policy documents, and case studies relevant to your value chain and context. Organise the review according to the eight leverage point categories, identifying documented examples of interventions and their outcomes. Pay particular attention to contexts with similar environmental, social, or institutional characteristics but maybe in other geographical locations. Be explicit about the evidence base supporting each potential leverage point, noting any gaps or uncertainties.
1. **Designing and Facilitating Stakeholder and Policy Workshops:** They are most effective when they bring together diverse stakeholders with genuine decision-making influence or lived

⁹ Deliverable 2.4 can be accessed [here](#).

experience. Key design considerations include:

- a) **Stakeholder mapping:** Identify all relevant actors across the value chain, including producers, traders, processors, consumers, government agencies, civil society organisations, and research institutions before planning the workshop
 - b) **Gender balance and inclusivity:** Ensure representation of marginalized groups. Explicitly seek gender balance and representation of historically excluded groups (e.g. women, Indigenous Peoples, youth). Consider whether separate sessions or tailored facilitation approaches might be needed to ensure all voices are raised and heard;
 - c) **Facilitation approach:** Use participatory methods such as world cafés, participatory ranking exercises, scenario planning, and visual mapping. Ensure facilitators are culturally competent and skilled in managing power dynamics;
 - d) **Documentation:** Record discussions, capture visual outputs (e.g., flip charts, maps), and document both consensus and dissenting views. Participant consent should be obtained for all documentation;
 - e) **Follow-up:** These stakeholder engagement activities should not be one-off events. Plan for follow-up engagement to share results, refine proposals and results, and support implementation.
2. **Qualitative Thematic Analysis and Synthesis:** After completing both literature reviews and stakeholder and policy workshops, systematically compare the leverage points identified through each method. Look for commonalities (indicating robust, widely recognised opportunities), divergences (indicating different strategic emphases or knowledge gaps), and complementarities (where different methods provide different but mutually reinforcing insights). Use the analysis to design integrated interventions that combine theoretical insights with practical, context-appropriate strategies.

4.2 AVAILABLE TOOLS AND RESSOURCES

In the course of the BIOTRAILS project several tools were developed to support the development of transitional pathways in biodiversity relevant supply chains. A short overview will be given in the following. A detailed description can be found in Deliverable 2.4¹⁰.

- **Serious Game:** A behavioural interventional toolkit for consumers to increase their awareness of the biodiversity impacts of their consumption.
- **Biodiversity-Focused ESG Toolkit:** Aims to support corporates to incorporate biodiversity aspects in their ESG policies by empowering companies to assess and quantify their biodiversity impacts.
- **Behavioural Interventional Toolkit:** This tool aims to support the uptake of biodiversity-friendly actions of consumers.
- **Visualisation of Alternative Scenarios:** By showcasing how different sustainability scenarios impact the supply chain, real change can be implemented by data driven decision making.
- **Opportunities for Cities to reduce their Biodiversity Impacts:** By providing a new framework, this tool help cities to reduce their biodiversity impacts on three scopes: local, regional and global.

There are several additional tools and resources, which can further support practitioners to apply

¹⁰ For a more detailed description, see: [Deliverable 2.4](#)

the frameworks and methodologies. They are introduced in the following but only described in greater detail in Deliverable 2.4¹¹.

- **Participatory Methods Guides:** Numerous resources exist for designing and facilitating participatory workshops, including guides from organisations such as the International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED), the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), and the World Resources Institute (WRI). These guides provide step-by-step instructions for participatory rural appraisal, stakeholder mapping, scenario planning, and other relevant methods.
- **Certification and Traceability Systems:** Several third-party certification schemes can support transparency and sustainable practices, including Fairtrade International, Rainforest Alliance, Marine Stewardship Council, and the Forest Stewardship Council. Blockchain-based traceability platforms are increasingly available, though their accessibility to smallholder producers varies.
- **Financing Mechanisms:** Potential sources of financing for value chain transformation include the Global Environment Facility (GEF), the Green Climate Fund (GCF), national environment funds, corporate sustainability programmes, impact investment funds, and payments for ecosystem services schemes. Technical assistance in accessing these mechanisms is often available through development agencies and non-governmental organisations.
- **Knowledge Platforms:** Online platforms such as the IPBES Knowledge and Data Portal, the Convention on Biological Diversity's Clearing-House Mechanism, and regional sustainable agriculture networks provide access to research, case studies, and best practices. These platforms facilitate knowledge exchange and support evidence-based decision-making.

Conclusion

This report demonstrates that the methodology developed in the project and Deliverables 2.3 and 2.4, provides a robust, flexible, and effective way for designing context-specific pathways towards transformative change in biodiversity-relevant value chains. The successful application across four different case studies confirms the methodology's transferability. The four case studies represent diverse sectors, geographies, production systems, and sustainability challenges, yet the consistent three-stage methodology enabled systematic identification of strategic intervention points in each context. The key to the methodology's effectiveness lies in its structured flexibility. Whilst the conceptual foundations and procedural steps remain consistent, the design explicitly requires and facilitates adaptation to local conditions.

For practitioners and policymakers seeking to apply this methodology elsewhere, several principles are critical. First, the methodology should be systematically adapted to the specific context. Second, participatory stakeholder engagement is essential. While the literature-based analysis provides theoretical breadth, the stakeholder knowledge ensures the contextual relevance, practical feasibility, and local legitimacy. Third, the comparative synthesis between literature-based and stakeholder-identified leverage points reveals where global evidence converges with local priorities and where context-specific adaptation is necessary. Fourth, successful application requires investment in inclusive workshop design, culturally appropriate facilitation, and sustained stakeholder dialogue beyond one-off consultations.

The methodology has proven effective across varying value chains: from agricultural commodities to extractive industries, from smallholder-dominated systems to industrial production, and from terrestrial to marine ecosystems. This demonstrates its general adaptability to new sectors and geographies. However, the successful application depends highly on the local context and its enabling conditions, such as institutional capacity, stakeholder willingness to engage, the availability of financing mechanisms, and general political commitment to support transformative

¹¹ For a more detailed description, see: [Deliverable 2.4](#)

change.

The tools and resources developed in the BIOTRAILS project provide additional support, but they complement rather than replace the core methodology. Ultimately, it should be kept in mind, that the pathways for transformative change represent context-appropriate strategies grounded in both scientific evidence and stakeholder visions. The methodology presented here offers practitioners a structured, participatory, and scientifically informed approach that is transferable across different value chains and contexts when adapted thoughtfully to local realities.

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